

1 **Control of genes required for antigen presentation by dominant negative p53.**

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6 We measured total transcription in human cells expressing a dominant negative p53 mutant, R175H, to
7 understand how p53 mutations found in humans with cancer influence expression of genes that function in
8 antigen presentation. We discovered important changes in expression of transcriptional regulators of
9 class I and class II antigen presentation, in expression of genes that function in the antigen presentation
10 pathway like beta-2-microglobulin, and genes important for providing co-stimulatory interactions between
11 antigen presenting cells and T-cells or B-cells.
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Results

We studied control of antigen presentation by dominant negative by measuring total transcription in human cells (MCF10A) expressing a dominant negative p53 mutation, R175H.

I. The expression of the transcriptional activator of MHC class II genes *CIITA* is silenced by p53 R175H.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4261	3.18E-02	2.038	2.146455	4.3744036	52.59	CIITA	559/14219	96.1

II. The expression of *NLRC5*, a transcriptional activator of MHC class I genes, is weakly but modestly enhanced by p53 R175H.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84166	1.95E-01	2.38	-1.296953	-3.0873697	56.69	NLRC5	8664/14219	39.1

III. Class II component *B2M* and other genes important for antigen presentation is modulated by p53 R175H.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
6891	9.94E-01	0.768	-0.007946	-0.0060994	428.5	TAP2	4606/14219	67.6
6890	4.97E-01	1.279	0.678429	0.8677101	134.18	TAP1	4608/14219	67.6
5696	6.32E-01	1.33	-0.479397	-0.6376075	148.3	PSMB8	4607/14219	67.6
567	1.09E-01	0.76	-1.602772	-1.2173914	539.34	B2M	1243/14219	91.3

IV. Control of cathepsin V is regulated by p53 R175H.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1515	4.94e-02	1.548	1.964748	3.0423781	86.51	CTSV	734/14219	94.8

V. Control of non-classical MHC antigen presentation is influenced by p53 R175H.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
3140	7.99e-01	1.984	0.2546	0.5052468	63.5	MR1	2173/14219	98.8

VI. Cluster of differentiation (CD) genes that serve as markers of functional T and B lymphocytes and antigen presenting cells (in providing co-stimulatory interactions) are perturbed by p53 R175H.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
100133941	1.73E-02	0.734	2.380756	1.746576	1125.98	CD24	378/14219	97.3
958	1.98E-02	3.399	2.330115	7.9205638	36.71	CD40	420/14219	97.0
966	1.01E-01	0.599	-1.638575	-0.9808884	1908.76	CD59	1184/14219	91.7
965	8.20E-01	2.054	-0.227774	-0.4677443	68.52	CD58	1909/14219	86.6

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Discussion

We described here control of a network of genes required for antigen presentation by a p53 mutant that causes transformation and transformation-resultant disease (cancer) in humans, p53 R175H. This included genes required for proteolytic processing of antigen like cathepsin V, genes required for extracellular presentation on MHC like B2M, genes that provide essential co-stimulatory signals at the immunological synapse to B and T cells like CD24 and CD40, and the master regulator of class II gene expression, CIITA.

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Methods

We used RNA-sequencing data from GSE162341 ($n=2$ MCF10A expressing wild-type p53 and $n=1$ MCF10A expressing p53 R175H) and R-based computational methods for this study.